

ECHO

Cancer Mission Hubs

Business Continuity Framework

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Executive Summary

This report presents the outcomes of Task 5.2 within Work Package 5 of the ECHO S project, which aims to support the long-term sustainability of a future European Network of National Cancer Mission Hubs (NCMHs). The task directly contributes to ECHO S General Objective 4 - *To create the foundations for a European network of NCMHs by developing a business continuity and operations model framework* - by developing an operational blueprint for the governance, financing, and business continuity of the network, drawing on lessons learned from established European cancer organisations and networks.

The analysis is grounded in a multi-phase methodology combining benchmarking, surveys, in-depth interviews, and an ecosystem and needs analysis. In Phase 1, a structured survey captured qualitative insights from seven well-established European cancer networks regarding their governance structures, financing models, membership arrangements, services, monitoring practices, and communication strategies. Phase 2 complemented these findings through in-depth interviews, allowing for deeper exploration of organisational diversity, alternative funding mechanisms, performance measurement approaches, and sustainability strategies. Phase 3 expanded the perspective to a broader ecosystem level by engaging stakeholders representing the Penta Helix model during the ECHO S General Assembly, capturing expectations, perceived benefits, and anticipated challenges related to the future European Network of NCMHs.

The results highlight several common patterns across existing European cancer networks. Effective governance relies on clear strategic oversight, defined roles and responsibilities, transparency, and regular reporting, while flexibility is maintained through continuous communication and member consultation. Financing models are predominantly based on EU and grant funding, often complemented by membership fees, sponsorships, or service-based revenues. Networks primarily deliver value through networking, training, participation in EU projects, and knowledge exchange, while systematic monitoring commonly relies on member surveys, activity evaluations, and key performance indicators such as membership growth, members' satisfaction, and project effectiveness.

Building on these findings, the report proposes a portfolio of alternative scenarios for governance, financing, and business continuity. Four governance models, four financing models, and four business continuity models are described, each with associated strengths and limitations. These scenarios are not intended as

prescriptive solutions but as adaptable reference frameworks that can be combined while taking into consideration challenges of local NMCH resulting, from their national specificities.

Overall, the report provides a structured foundation to inform future decision-making and stakeholder discussions, which will be further refined and validated through Focus Group consultations in cooperation with Task 5.3.

Introduction

The core goal of the ECHO S project is to support the implementation of EU Mission on Cancer objectives through the creation of National Cancer Mission Hubs (NCMHs) in each Member State and Associated Country.

To facilitate implementation, these NCMHs should stay connected in a European Network guaranteeing sharing of best practices, knowledge and collaboration opportunities. The objective of WP5 is directly contributing to ECHO S General Objective 4, *to lay the foundations for a future European Network of NCMHs and its sustainability*, by developing an operational blueprint of the future EU network of NCMHs. In order to do so, the scope of work related to the report takes into account the outcomes and outputs prepared by the WP2 such as concept models aimed at proposing minimal criteria for inclusion to become NCMH, manual with guidelines for the creation of NCMHs as well as the internal knowledge sharing program to facilitate best practice sharing and mutual learning among ECHO S' organisations.

The main goal the task 5.2 was to propose a governance structure, to sustain long-term activities of the network. To tackle this issue, it was decided to necessary to identify European cancer organisations with their experience and potential to engage in cooperative activities. Such scanning was done in order to articulate the scope and positioning of the future EU network of NCMHs having in mind any potential overlap caused by competitive activities.¹ Moreover, learning from the experience of renowned European cancer networks gave an input for creation of a roadmap on how to make the EU network of NCMHs sustainable in the future (Task 5.3). Such approach, combined with the task 5.2 output of alternative scenarios for governance, finance and business structures can make it possible to create a viable outline for the operability of the EU network of NCMHs in the coming years.

This document summarizes the work of Task 5.2 and presents a portfolio of alternative scenarios for the governance, financial, and business models of the future European Network of NCMHs.

¹ ECHO S – Establishing of Cancer Mission Hubs: Networks and Synergies, Proposal template Part B: technical description.

Methodology

Within WP5, task 5.2 focuses on defining a suitable governance structure, including finance and business strategies to sustain long-term activities of the network. This work builds on the experience of established European and international health-related networks that have demonstrated resilience, continuity, and operational viability over time.

To initiate the work, a benchmarking exercise was carried out covering associations, federations, societies, agencies, coalitions, NGOs, public and private non-profit organisations, research infrastructures, etc. operating at European level. These activities targeted representatives of European transnational networks active in the cancer domain. Particular attention was given to organisations with strong interconnections and active involvement of civil society, including individual citizens and patients. A technical review of publicly available resources supported the identification of a final set of relevant networks, which were subsequently invited to a survey aimed at identifying key structural elements related to governance, financing, and operational models. The list of organisations was defined within the framework of the ECHO S project “Establishing of Cancer Mission Hubs: Networks and Synergies”². Respondents held managerial or coordination positions and contributed on behalf of their organisations. Once identified, the representatives of the same networks were then interviewed in 2 steps: Phase 1: Initial Survey and Phase 2: In-depth interviews. The conclusions made from both interactions were then expanded in the last part – Phase 3: Ecosystem and Needs Analysis Survey.

Phase 1: Survey

Between November 2024 and February 2025, Phase 1 survey was disseminated to European networks and institutions³. The objective of this phase was to gather insights into institutional experience related to the creation, governance and operation of international partner networks. The responders held managerial positions and spoke on behalf of their organisations’ experience. The survey consisted of 33 multiple choice, open-ended and rating questions. It was

² [ECHO S: Establishing of Cancer Mission Hubs: Networks and Synergies](#)

³ See Appendix I, Phase 1: Questionnaire for the First Round of Interviews

developed using MS Office Forms and designed to take approximately 40 minutes to complete. The questions were organised into 9 thematic blocks covering:

- Background
- Governance and Structure
- Finance models
- Business continuity
- Services
- Monitoring
- Public Relations Strategy
- Future and Sustainable Development
- Lessons Learned

Phase 2: In-depth interviews

The initial survey was followed by in-depth interviews⁴ aimed at clarifying and contextualising previously provided answers. This step also enabled the systematic integration of respondents' practical experience into a set of recommendations to inform the design and development of the future European Network of NCMHs, in line with the ECHO S project timeline. The in-depth interviews were conducted as 30-minute online meetings with five respondents, with one respondent choosing to provide input in written form via email.

The interview questions expanded on responses submitted in the Phase 1 survey, particularly in cases where participants selected "other(s)". In these instances, the ECHO S team followed up with additional questions to better understand the context and rationale behind the respondents' inputs.

Phase 3: Ecosystem and Needs Analysis Survey

The Ecosystem of the future network is shaped by interactions between the key stakeholder groups forming the Penta Helix model: Business, Health & Care, Knowledge & Academia, Citizens & Civil Society and Public Administration.

⁴ See Appendix 2, Phase 2: In-depth Interview, pp. 57-58.

Understanding the needs, engagement dynamics and challenges of these groups is crucial for planning sustainable and long-lasting structures at both local and European levels, while considering the diverse context from different Member States and Associated Countries (MS/AC). The analysis was carried out through a survey⁵ (Appendix 3) administered during the ECHO S General Assembly meeting held in Brussels on the 25th of June. The primary objective was to collect feedback from different stakeholder representing the different Penta Helix groups regarding their perceptions of the European Network of NCMH, including its operability, challenges, potential needs and benefits.

In addition, the survey explored stakeholders' views on how the future network could:

- Strengthen national collaboration in the field of Oncology across the stakeholder groups
- Accelerate the translation of research into clinical practice
- Improve access to knowledge and research tools
- Address key stakeholders' priorities
- Enhance patient-centred approaches

A summary of the responses, presented in a visual format, is provided in the corresponding chapter.

⁵ See Appendix 3, Phase 3: Ecosystem and Needs Analysis.

Results

Phase 1: Initial Survey

The survey⁶ was sent out to European institutions and networks. Seven out of fourteen answered and 6 subsequently participated in the in-depth interviews. The organisations were as follows:

Table 1. European organisations participating in the survey

#	Name of the institution	Headquarter city
1	European School of Oncology (ESO)	Italy
2	Organisation of European Cancer Institutes – European Economic Interest Grouping (OECI-EEIG)	Belgium
3	European Organization for Research and Treatment of Cancer (EORTC)	Belgium
4	ERN for Rare Adult Solid Tumours - EURACAN	France
5	European Society for Radiotherapy and Oncology (ESTRO)	Belgium
6	Association of European Cancer Leagues (ECL)	Belgium
7	European Network of Cancer Registries (ENCR)	Italy

1. Governance structure

71% of the respondents represented senior or upper management positions within their organisations. Others represented Board or hybrid form. When asked about the main elements of their networks' organisational structures, respondents selected the options presented in Figure 1. Notably, none of the respondents identified a Network Board as part of their formal governance structure.

⁶ For the list of all questions, See Appendix 1: Questionnaire for the Initial Survey (Phase 1), pp. 39-49.

Figure 1. Number and type of responders' representation in their organisations.

In response to the question “*What roles and responsibilities do the board members have?*”, all respondents highlighted strategic management (7) as a core responsibility. A majority also selected representing the organisation (6), operational oversight (5) and financial decisions (5). Additional roles mentioned included planning (3) and relationship building (3).

Regarding operational maturity, all respondents confirmed that their networks existed for more than five years. In the multiple-choice question: *What are the fundamental management principles and procedures in your Network/Organisation?*, all respondents, identified strategic planning and reporting (7) as key elements. Most also indicated accountability principles and regular meetings (6). Other practices reported included transparency (5), integrity (4), regulatory compliance (3), risk assessment (2) and internal audits (2).

Figure 2. Fundamental management principles and procedures in a network

In a subsequent question, respondents were asked to rank the management principles and procedures listed above according to their level of importance. Among these, reporting, strategic planning and regular meetings were consistently identified as the most important, with these elements most frequently assigned to the “critical” category.

Figure 3. Importance of managerial principles and procedures according to responders

As for the mechanisms used to ensure management flexibility in addressing the diverse needs of the members, respondents most frequently identified surveys (6), consultations with members (5), constant communication (4) and quick decision making (4).

Figure 4. Mechanisms and tools used to ensure flexibility in a network

2. Financing

Subsequent questions focused on financing options supporting networks activities. Most respondents indicated grants and EU funds as their primary source of financing. Accordingly, the predominant fundraising strategy reported was the submission of grant applications.

Figure 5. Sources of financing in networks

3. Membership and its benefits

When asked about requirements for becoming a member of an organisation/network, responses most frequently identified compliance with specific formal requirements (5), active involvement in the field of oncology (5) and agreement with the network’s regulations (4).

Figure 6. Membership requirements

In the subsequent sections of the survey, respondents were asked to identify the benefits offered to network members. Reported benefits included participation in events, access to training opportunities, involvement in European projects, and access to clinical trials. One respondent highlighted that the benefits provided depend on the level of membership, with a member's status within the network determined by the extent of their engagement in network activities.

All responses, grouped according to the proposed categories, are presented below according to the level of frequency:

Event participation:

- Free participation to all the activities of the Grouping, including the main annual event,
- Participation to twinning with cancer centres outside the EU
- Involvement in the development of supports like guidelines
- Opportunity to feed into important areas, e.g. the 5th revision of the new European Code Against Cancer
- Discounts to events
- Representation in the only platform of exchange exclusively for member leagues at the national and regional level.
- Participation in various working groups such as: ECL Patient Support Working Group, ECL Prevention & Early Detection Working, ECL Task Force for Equal Access to Cancer Training and mentoring opportunities:
 - Free participation to the training courses
 - Training and education for associate members and early career investigators
 - Training, education and participation to various fora for corresponding members
 - Expertise for the management of rare cancers recognised at the European level by the EC
- Engage in opportunities to network with international peers when ECL organises international meetings such as the ECL Annual Conferences or meetings in Brussels related to the EU institutions.

Accreditation Program:

- Participation to the Accreditation and Designation Program based on a fee

EU-based projects involvement:

- The opportunity to contribute to cancer control advocacy at the European Union on crucial policies and EU-funded projects.
- Involvement in EC projects or other International activities

Others:

- Access to clinical trials,
- ERN logo
- Access to paid journals and professional press
- Voting rights in decision taking within a network
- Updates on initiatives and meetings at the EU and pan-European level, in Brussels, in EU or non-EU European countries.
- Equality between Member States and leagues of different sizes through financial support for those with lower incomes.
- Data sharing among members

In response to the question on the scope of services offered, four respondents indicated that services are provided exclusively to members, while the remaining three reported that their services are available to a broader audience beyond network membership (for everyone).

When asked to specify the types of services, support, and tools offered, most respondents identified networking activities (7) and training opportunities (6) as their primary services. Notably, among all responses received, only one organisation reported providing access to specific research tools, such as quality-of-life (QoL) instruments.

Figure 7. Services offered in networks

4. Network and activities' monitoring and evaluation

When asked “What methods do you use to monitor and evaluate the activities of your Network/Organisation?”, most respondents indicated member surveys (5), regular analysis (4) and evaluations (4).

Figure 8. Monitoring and evaluation of network and its activities

The most used KPI indicators for assessing the success of a network or/and organisation included number of members (6), member satisfaction (5) and project effectiveness (4).

Figure 9. Examples of KPIs used in networks

5. Communication

When asked about communication channels, most respondents indicated newsletters (7), social media (6) and face-to-face meetings (6) as the most effective ones to reach their members and stakeholders.

Figure 10. Modes of communication

6. Challenges and lessons learned

Most respondents indicated the following categories of challenges within their networks

- Establishing shared vision and goals
- Securing initial funding and resources
- Gaining Credibility and Recognition
- Building Trust Among Members
- Navigating Diverse Policy and Healthcare Systems
- Maintaining Engagement and Momentum

When asked about the type of advice respondents would give to a newly emerging network, transparency in communication and securing financial resources were highlighted as one of the key answers. Other replies included:

- Deliver robust added value to your stakeholders

- Involve strong leaders with a well-known expertise and a strong coordination team
- Make sure the objectives can be reachable
- Manage resources wisely; engage members; sustainable growth.
- Careful management of governance structure.
- Creating and sustaining a successful network requires strategic planning, strong collaboration, and adaptability

Phase 2: In depth interviews

The decision to conduct in-depth interviews⁷ stemmed from the need to further explore and clarify the responses collected during the first phase. While the initial survey provided valuable quantitative insights into governance, financing, membership, and communication structures within existing European cancer networks, many respondents selected “other” options or provided open-ended comments that indicated more complex or context-specific practices not fully captured by predefined survey categories.

Analysis of the “other” responses submitted by surveyed organisations revealed several important areas requiring deeper exploration. Respondents highlighted additional aspects such as unique organisational structures, alternative funding mechanisms, diverse evaluation methods, and strategies for ensuring sustainability and continuity of operations.

⁷ For the list of all questions, See Appendix 2: In-depth interview (Phase 2), pp. 50-51.

Table 2. “Other” responses by type of question and organisation

Organisation A	Organisation B	Organisation C	Organisation D	Organisation E	Organisation F
Other elements of the organizational structure	Other strategies used for fundraising	Other sources of funding	No tools and resources indicated for members for activities	Other sources of funding	Other sources of funding
Other sources of funding	Other services and support offered for members	Other KPI	No innovations planned for improving activities and services	Other monitoring and evaluation activity methods	Other fundraising strategies
No strategies used for sustainable development and continuity of operations?			No strategies used for sustainable development and continuity of operations		

For example, some networks referred to specific tools and services offered to members, different sources of financial support beyond EU grants, or distinct approaches to monitoring and assessment not covered in the standard survey options. In a few cases, respondents indicated the absence of formal strategies for sustainability, suggesting varying levels of organisational maturity among networks.

These findings emphasized the necessity of conducting in-depth interviews to further investigate:

- organisational models and internal governance mechanisms
- broader and alternative funding sources
- long-term strategies for sustainable development and operational continuity.

For example, the Organisation B highlighted the role of strategic partnerships beyond EU grants as part of its fundraising strategy. It also noted that, for events it organizes, the institution itself covers no more than 30% of the total costs, with the remaining share co-funded by participating cancer centres as

a means of promoting their visibility and collaboration. Additionally, OECl maintains a Board of Young Scientists, which convenes regularly via online meetings, offering a structured platform for continuous professional exchange and engagement among emerging researchers.

Similarly, the Organisation C outlined a diversified funding model that includes foundations, charities, donors, and corporate social responsibility (CSR) contributions, typically allocated to specific strategic or project-based goals. It also described a sophisticated approach to measuring performance, with key performance indicators (KPIs) linked to its clinical trial activities. These include metrics such as the number and distribution of trials by country, institution, and year, the evolution of participation over time, patient entry points, interest in clinical trials, and the number of scientific publications generated.

Other surveyed networks mentioned additional non-standard funding and evaluation mechanisms or, in some cases, the absence of formal sustainability strategies - underscoring the diversity in maturity levels and operational approaches across European cancer organizations.

Phase 3: Ecosystem and Needs Analysis Survey

The Ecosystem and Needs analysis Survey⁸ was conducted on June 24th, 2025, in Brussels, during the General Assembly meeting. The survey aimed to capture participants' perceptions of the European network of national cancer mission hubs, as well as perceived benefits and challenges associated to this particular network, both at individual level and across the network as a whole.

⁸ For all questions, See Appendix 3: Ecosystem and Needs Analysis (Phase 3), p. 52.

Figure 11. Types of stakeholders represented at the General Assembly meeting

The stakeholder composition of the meeting was predominantly composed of research actors (universities/research institutes/scientific societies), followed by policymakers and “other” public bodies (regulatory/governmental/regional administrations). Patients and Patient Advocacy Groups, as well as healthcare providers, were represented to a lesser extent, while industry stakeholders constituted the smallest group.

The responses to question: “*What activities can you – as a representative of the selected stakeholder group – add to the EU network of NCMHs?*”, are listed in the table below. Activities listed by respondents in the Ecosystem and Needs analysis were grouped arbitrary by the Task 5.2 team.

Table 3. Summary of question: “*What activities can you – as a representative of the selected Stakeholder group – add to the EU Network of NCMHs*”

Stakeholder type	Activities to be added to the EU Network of NCMHs
Healthcare (hospitals, HCPs, pharmacies, eHealth)	Clinical knowledge, country specific knowledge on certain topics for sharing best practices,
Patients (PAGs, Carers etc)	EU wide patient advocacy, Patient-diverse expertise, Innovation focus from patient involvement in HTA, Advocacy capacitation, co-creation of research perspective with patients
Researchers (universities, research institutes, scientific)	Academic research and studies to support cancer hub improvement, co-creation of research perspective with patients, data-driven approach, education and research

societies)	activities, academic conferences on particular topics, training experience, joint submissions of new research in cancer field, preparation and implementation of research programmes, advanced EU-wide cancer collaboration through cross-boarded research, representing research institutions' interests.
Policymakers (Ministries of Health, Ministries of Science, etc.)	Policy alignment, being an interface between the hub and the EU policy developments, knowledge on EU funding, funding, expertise with policy recommendations and policy related activities, public health aspects, networks and synergies from other projects and programmes
Others (regulatory agencies, governmental bodies, regional and local administration, public services)	Sharing of expertise on what we do for the hub at national level, sharing of expertise on what we do for the hub at national level, policy dialogues, thematic workshops, coordination of the NCMH, connecting all country ecosystem in one, methodology on how to measure the collaboration between NCMHs and the impact in the EU network, governance of the network at the EU level, integrating the needs of local stakeholders, experience from the national context and expectations from national stakeholders. Link with the national stakeholder's information on National Cancer Plan, funding, expertise with policy recommendations and policy related activities. Public health aspects, networks and synergies from other projects and programmes

When asked about the challenges that the future European network of NCMHs may encounter, the majority of respondents pointed out the complexities regarding the managerial, political, financial and cultural aspects of it. The challenges defined by respondents can be categorised as follows:

- **Managerial:** lack of organisational support, insufficient time for all proposed activities, engaging different stakeholders, potential difficulties in collaboration, lack of direction on how to participate in the EU network
- **Political:** lack of consensus on the goal and purpose of the NCMH, conflicts between stakeholders disrupting the implementation process, lack of interest on the output, Misalignment of the needs and expectations with those at the national level, low engagement of stakeholders at the national level, balancing powers of Penta Helix.

- **Financial:** insufficient resources, sustainability issues, budget allocations, national funding will not prioritize unless clear goals, not sufficient return on investment
- **Ecosystem specific challenges (Needs-analysis relevant challenges):** low coverage and interest due to other priorities, definition and identification of innovations in cancer field, different goals for NCMH and the EU network, presence of similar organizations in a country

Participants highlighted that the main benefits of the future European network of NCMHs lie in enhanced knowledge and expertise exchange, collaboration, and networking across countries. The network enables joint efforts, shared resources and funding mechanisms, and faster implementation of initiatives. It also supports the alignment of national actions, increases visibility, and creates a unified voice to influence European policies. Respondents also noted benefits such as avoiding duplication, promoting innovation, ensuring the sustainability of the Cancer Mission beyond individual projects, and providing an inclusive, neutral space for stakeholders to work together.

For individuals, the main benefits of integrating the future European network of NCMHs include opportunities to share and gain expertise, access practical tools, training, and best practices, and benefit from expanded networking opportunities across Europe. Participants value the ability to collaborate, exchange ideas, and connect with diverse stakeholders, including policymakers and private partners, within a well-connected and supportive ecosystem. The network also offers visibility and recognition, supports alignment of projects and national initiatives, and provides inspiration and learning through exposure to new approaches. Overall, individuals benefit from a sense of belonging to a community of like-minded professionals working collectively to improve cancer care in Europe.

There is strong overlap between the benefits identified for the European network as a whole and those for individuals participating in the European Network of NCMHs. In both cases, respondents emphasised the importance of:

- knowledge and expertise exchange (learning, sharing best practices, access to tools and training)
- collaboration and networking (cross-border cooperation, connecting with colleagues and stakeholders)
- increased visibility and influence (both for individuals and for the network collectively)

However, there can also be found distinct differences:

- At the network level, the focus is on collective impact, including policy influence, avoiding duplication, mobilising funding, ensuring sustainability, and creating a unified European voice.
- At the individual level, the emphasis shifts towards personal and professional development, notably gaining skills, inspiration, access to information, recognition, and connections that can strengthen one's own work or institution.

Based on frequency of responses and emphasis placed by participants, the three most important shared benefits across both individual and network levels are:

1. **Knowledge exchange and learning opportunities** — cited as the top benefit at both levels.
2. **Networking and collaboration** — building relationships and sharing expertise across borders.
3. **Visibility and influence** — enhancing both personal recognition and the network's collective voice in shaping European cancer policies.

Alignment with WP 5.1

The conclusions made in the Ecosystem and Needs Analysis regarding the activities that may be offered to the European network of NCMHs, seem to match the activities that were identified by experts from 21 Members States and Associated Countries⁹. In the document called "Positioning the future EU network of NCMHs in the European cancer landscape, which presents the work done in task 5.1, the activities that the EU network of NCMHs may be performing are as follows (in the order from highest to lowest priority):

- Supporting the setup of NCMHs in Member State/Associated Country

⁹ [Positioning the future EU network of NCMHs in the European cancer landscape, 3.2.4 Activities, p. 18.](#)

- Offering trainings and workshops for capacitation
- Facilitating the collaboration of NCMHs with other EU projects
- Monitoring the NCMHs
- Serving as a contact point between the European Commission and the NCMHs.

The greatest importance of all of the above points was given to supporting activities in setting up the NCMHs and to knowledge exchange opportunities which confirms the expectations of respondents outlined during the Ecosystem and Needs Analysis.

Limitations

Despite the comprehensive and multi-phase methodology used in Task 5.2, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the number of participating European networks in Phase 1 was relatively limited, with seven organisations responding out of fourteen invited. While these organisations are well-established and highly relevant to the cancer domain, their experiences may not fully capture the diversity of governance and operational practices across all European cancer-related networks as 7 out of 14 haven't answered to our survey invitation

Second, the analysis relies primarily on self-reported data collected through surveys and interviews. As a result, responses may reflect institutional perspectives, priorities, or interpretations that are influenced by organisational culture, maturity, or strategic positioning. Although the in-depth interviews helped clarify and contextualise survey findings, some nuances and informal practices may remain underrepresented.

Third, the Ecosystem and Needs Analysis was conducted during a single General Assembly meeting, which may have influenced stakeholder representation. Research and policy actors were more strongly represented than patients, healthcare providers, and industry stakeholders. Consequently, some perspectives - particularly those of patients and private-sector actors - may be less prominent in the findings.

Finally, the proposed governance, financing, and business continuity scenarios are based on current practices and experiences of existing networks and do not yet reflect empirical testing within the future European Network of NCMHs. Their

practical feasibility, effectiveness, and adaptability across different national contexts will require further validation through Focus Groups, pilot implementation, and iterative refinement.

Business continuity framework: Before Focus Group

To support the establishment of a European Network of NCMHs, this analysis aims to present potential scenarios for developing governance, financing, and business continuity models. Drawing on an assessment of existing European societies and networks, several key features were identified as common and effective across most organisations (See Figure 12).

Figure 12. Key elements identified by survey respondents as important for developing possible scenarios for the management, financing, and continuity of operations for future network of NMCHs

These features can serve as a reference framework to guide the creation of the future European Network of NCMHs. The objective of this exercise is not to prescribe a single model, but rather to provide practical examples and successful approaches that ECHO S can tailor to the specific characteristics, maturity, and contextual circumstances of the established hubs in different MS

The following section outlines potential core elements of governance, financial, and continuity models. These proposed elements will be further explored and validated during the upcoming Focus Groups, where input from diverse stakeholders will help refine and authenticate the recommendations.

In selecting scenarios for the final governance, financial, and business continuity model, it is essential that the EU Network of National Mission Cancer

Hubs (NMCHs) anticipates and accounts for the heterogeneity of Member State policies. These policies define the legal, institutional, and operational frameworks under which NMCHs are able to participate in EU-level cooperation. As a result, Member State policies can significantly influence the depth, scope, and intensity of NMCH participation under each proposed scenario.

To ensure equitable and inclusive participation across all Member States, despite differences in national mandates, legal frameworks, and institutional capacities, the design of the EU NMCH Network should incorporate targeted adaptations to the proposed scenarios. These adaptations may include the following elements:

Differentiated roles, allowing for varying levels of engagement, such as:

- Full Members
- Associated Members
- Observers

Optional governance layers, enabling modular participation according to national mandates and capacities:

- Strategic Layer (Board / Executive Board)
- Operational Layer (Steering Committee / Working Groups)
- Consultative Layer (General Assembly / NMCH Forum)

Policy-safe participation modes, ensuring compliance with national legal and policy constraints, including:

- Non-binding participation formats, such as guidelines, best practices, soft-law instruments, and recommendations.

Furthermore, as the number of formally recognised NMCHs continues to grow, it becomes increasingly important to actively involve their representatives in Focus Group discussions. This will ensure that diverse national perspectives, constraints, and expectations are adequately reflected in the refinement of the final governance, financing, and business continuity models.

Governance Models

Following the definition of Chartered Governance Institute UK & Ireland¹⁰, governance is understood as “framework by which organisations are directed and controlled. It identifies who can make decisions, who has the authority to act on behalf of the organisation and who is accountable for how an organisation and its people behave and perform. Good governance provides a framework for better decision-making. It permeates every level of an organisation, ensuring sustainability, promoting ethical conduct, and fostering stakeholder trust.”¹¹ The goal was to identify major elements of governance structure that may play dominant role in shaping a network’s governance. Based on the analysis carried out in the previous two rounds of interviews, we have defined the following governance structures that were visible in all interviewed organisations.

Structure	Strategic Role	Notes
1. General Assembly / General Meeting (4)	Legitimacy, approval of major decisions, member representation	Acts as a legitimacy and approval body across most models. Used strongly in Board-Led and Member-Driven models.
2. Board/Executive Board (5)	Strategic direction, <u>financial control</u> , <u>organisational oversight</u>	Central in all models except the Collaborative model , where power is shared.
3. Steering Committee (4)	Coordination, expert oversight, strategic implementation	Key for scientific/technical alignment and multi-stakeholder coordination
4. Working Groups/Task Forces/ Committees (6)	Operational execution, <u>expertise</u> , <u>member engagement</u>	Agile, specialised, main platform for collaboration and implementation

Comparison

- General Assembly sets **major organisational direction**.
- Steering Board is **execution-focused** with strong emphasis on operational oversight.
- Members’ Board acts as a **bridge between policy and implementation**, with strong compliance functions.

Figure 13. Governance structures dependent on their strategic role

¹⁰ Chartered Governance Institute UK & Ireland, <https://www.cgi.org.uk/resources/factsheets/factsheets/what-is-governance/>, accessed on 15 October 2025.

¹¹ Ibid.

It is important to note, that even though all respondents confirmed existence of the governance structures described above, the relative influence and applicability of these structures vary across organisations. Their relevance depends largely on the organisational lifecycle. Additionally, based on interactions between these governance structures, four distinct governance scenarios were identified. Each scenario represents a different combination of the above governance structures.

Scenario #1: Board-Led Strategic Governance Model

Board/Executive Board plays a central role by handling and making decisions regarding strategic planning, financial oversight and operational supervision. In this model, governance relies on clear roles, where reporting, accountability and transparency rules are well defined and communicated. Additional governance structures, which play minor role are General Assembly, Working Groups and Steering Committee.

Scenario #2: Member-Driven Participatory Model

Governance decisions are shaped by member input and member engagement. Governing bodies such as Board or Steering Committee rely on consultations with members and continuous communication when making strategic decisions. Engagement is additionally enriched by networking events and cyclical surveys.

Scenario #3: Multi-Stakeholder Governance Model

Governance is shared among multiple institutional stakeholders. In this model, all governing structures listed above shape decision making, however General Assembly is the least present. Additionally, such model is oriented towards multidisciplinary collaboration with EU bodies (e.g. JRC, IARC), national institutions, research centres and NGOs.

Scenario #4: Flexible Governance Model

Governance model, which emphasises rapid decision-making, adaptability and flexibility. This model is typically used in networks that respond to clinical changes and must act quickly to keep pace with fast changing environment. The dominant role is played by the Executive Board, Steering Committee and Working Groups. General Assembly is visible to a lesser extent.

Table 4. Proposed scenarios for governance structure: Pros and Cons

Governance structure	Pros	Cons
#1: Board-Led Strategic Governance Model	Managerial procedures and roles well defined and communicated. Faster decision making.	Additional governance structures such as General Assembly, Working Groups or Steering Committee may play minor role which may cause power concentration just in one organisational structure.
#2: Member-Driven	Strategy shaped and decision made by common	Decision-making may be less rapid due to the need

Participatory Model	members agreement. Allows for greater member engagement.	to reach common consensus of members.
#3: Multi-Stakeholder Governance Model	Ensures greater engagement of multiple interdisciplinary actors.	May be more time consuming and problematic to reach agreement. Decisions take time.
#4: Flexible Governance Model	Adapts quickly to fast-changing environment.	Depending on the need, different organisational structures will play major role in decision-making, which may create inconsistency.

Finance Models

In this part of the analysis, we examined different sources of financing and fundraising strategies and as a result, four scenarios were identified, where usually one particular type of financing is dominant in each of the proposed scenarios.

Scenario #1: Membership-Based Financing Model

Funding is determined by different membership types (e.g. full, participatory, associate etc.). In some cases, members may attend General Assembly and decide on some organisational aspects, which may be strategy-based). This model aims to maintain ongoing members' engagement by offering activities and events for members. The main challenge identified in this model relates to always maintaining high quality standards to members.

Scenario #2: Grant-Funded Financing Model

Heavy reliance on external funding such as grants and EU funds. In this model, organisation's activities and areas of interest are usually tied to particular EU-funded projects and grants. Such financing model makes organisations vulnerable to time funding constraints, imposing at the same time relatively high administrative burden for regulatory, financial, reporting and auditing responsibilities.

Scenario #3: Sponsorship and Partnership Financing Model

Part of substantial budget comes from collaboration with private sector and sometimes with non-governmental organisations. The financing model in this case can be extended beyond grants and EU-funds, however funding heavily depends on strong relationship building and attracting sponsors as well as maintaining available financing options. What is more, this model requires high communication efforts and transparency standards in order to avoid potential conflicts of interest.

Scenario #4: Service Revenue or Mixed Revenue Model

Majority of income is generated through services offered. This model can also exist in a mixed form, where financial streams come from grants, sponsors, services and membership fees. The main drawback of this model is the need for substantial resources in designing and delivering services. It is also important to note that demand for some services offered may fluctuate.

Table 5. Proposed finance models: Pros and Cons

Finance models	Pros	Cons
#1: Membership-Based Financing Model	High quality services offered for members.	Financing largely depends on number of members, which makes this model vulnerable. New membership dependent on delivering high quality standards. Demand for particular services may fluctuate and change over time.
#2: Grant-Funded Financing Model	Opportunity to develop/enrich project management skills and specialise in particular project area of interest. Allows for multi-stakeholder participation.	Funding solely dependent on external sources. May involve greater administrative work. Financing is time limited.
#3: Sponsorship and Partnership Financing Model	Financing can come from different sources and be project-specific, focused on performing particular activities/work.	Requires strong relationship building and attracting new sponsors.

#4: Service Revenue or Mixed Revenue Model	Allows for greater diversification of resources and lower vulnerability to external resources.	Majority of income is generated through services offered which may fluctuate over time.
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Business Continuity Models

Business Continuity Model refers to all the organisational, technical and staffing measures used to ensure the continuation of operations. It also denotes strategic and tactical capability of an organisation to plan for and respond to incidents and business disruptions, enabling business operations to continue at an acceptable predefined level.¹² In this section, the objective was to identify existing models across organisations based on their governing rules and principles, as well as the type of activities they support. It is important to note, however, that the dominance of specific models varies depending on the organisation’s lifecycle of and the dynamics of the operating environment in which it functions.

Scenario #1: Management Procedures and Governance

Continuity approach built on structured governance, clear procedures and strategic oversight. It heavily relies on key continuity mechanisms such as regular reporting and monitoring, transparency and accountability, regulatory compliance, strategic planning and quality control. This model creates predictability and operational stability ensuring greater trust, which might be of particular importance to networks which are dependent on regulatory frameworks or EU Coordination mechanisms.

Scenario #2: Member Engagement and Communication

Continuity approach driven by active member participation, constant communication and high responsiveness to members’ needs. This model is characterised by relationship building and continuous feedback from members, which helps networks maintain high levels of membership engagement and commitment at the same time securing financial resources resulting from their participation.

¹² Open Risk Manual, < https://www.openriskmanual.org/wiki/Main_Page>, accessed on 5 October 2025.

Scenario #3: Financial Stability and Diversification

Continuity approach centred on having multiple financial streams and robust financial strategy. This model relies on financial income diversification, which reduces vulnerability and instability. It even allows networks to operate independently of a single funding source type.

Scenario #4: Flexibility and Rapid Response

Continuity approach driven by agility, fast decision making and capacity to respond to sudden environmental changes. Key mechanisms include emergency meetings and rapid coordination policies, strong internal communication and use of digital tools in order to enhance effective communication. This model makes it possible for a network to continue functioning during turmoil or sudden operational pressures allowing for flexibility and ability to innovative.

Table 6. Proposed business continuity models: Pros and Cons

Business continuity models	Pros	Cons
#1: Management Procedures and Governance	Creates predictability and operational stability ensuring greater trust.	May hinder rapid adaptation to fast-changing environment as it heavily relies on already established management mechanisms.
#2: Member Engagement and Communication	Allows for high level of membership engagement and high quality of services. Constant communication and responsiveness to members' needs is key.	May cause difficulties in defining activities that will fully engage members. May be challenging to analyse members' feedback and react accordingly in a timely manner.
#3: Financial Stability and Diversification	Reduces financial vulnerability thanks to income diversification. Work priorities well defined and planned.	Scope of work may be limited to a particular project funding.
#4: Flexibility and Rapid Response	Flexible and fast decision-making model. May be more appropriate to organisations with fragile external environments.	Less stable structure without developed mechanism of operability

Figure 14. Basis for various scenarios according to governance, financing and business continuity models

The above governance, finance, and business continuity scenarios are not mutually exclusive. They can be mixed and combined depending on their relevance, and the specific context of NCMHs integrating the network. The proposed set of scenarios represents an initial framework and will be presented and discussed during the Focus Group meeting which will be organised in cooperation with task 5.3. In the Focus Groups, the suggested models will be critically reviewed, discussed, and refined, and final conclusions and recommendations will be jointly agreed upon.

Table 7. Summary of proposed scenarios according to governance structure, financing and business continuity

Proposed scenario	Governance		Proposed scenario	Financing		Proposed scenario	Business continuity	
	Pros	Cons		Pros	Cons		Pros	Cons
#1: Board-Led Strategic Governance Model	Managerial procedures and roles well defined and communicated. Faster decision making.	Additional governance structures such as General Assembly, Working Groups or Steering Committee may play minor role which may cause power concentration just in one organisational structure.	#1: Membership-Based Financing Model	High quality services offered for members.	Financing largely depends on number of members, which makes this model vulnerable. New membership dependent on delivering high quality standards. Demand for particular services may fluctuate and change over time.	#1: Management Procedures and Governance	Creates predictability and operational stability ensuring greater trust.	May hinder rapid adaptation to fast-changing environment as it heavily relies on already established management mechanisms.
#2: Member-Driven Participatory Model	Strategy shaped and decision made by common members agreement. Allows for greater member engagement.	Decision-making may be less rapid due to the need to reach common consensus of members.	#2: Grant-Funded Financing Model	Opportunity to develop/enrich project management skills and specialise in particular project area of interest. Allows for multi-stakeholder participation.	Funding solely dependent on external sources. May involve greater administrative work. Financing is time limited.	#2: Member Engagement and Communication	Allows for high level of membership engagement and high quality of services. Constant communication and responsiveness to members' needs is key.	May cause difficulties in defining activities that will fully engage members. May be challenging to analyse members' feedback and react accordingly in a timely manner.
#3: Multi-Stakeholder Governance Model	Ensures greater engagement of multiple interdisciplinary actors.	May be more time consuming and problematic to reach agreement. Decisions take time.	#3: Sponsorship and Partnership Financing Model	Financing can come from different sources and be project-specific, focused on performing particular activities/work.	Requires strong relationship building and attracting new sponsors.	#3: Financial Stability and Diversification	Reduces financial vulnerability thanks to income diversification. Work priorities well defined and planned.	Scope of work may be limited to a particular project funding.
#4: Flexible Governance Model	Adapts quickly to fast-changing environment.	Depending on the need, different organisational structures will play major role in decision-making, which may create inconsistency.	#4: Service Revenue or Mixed Revenue Model	Allows for greater diversification of resources and lower vulnerability to external resources.	Majority of income is generated through services offered which may fluctuate over time.	#4: Flexibility and Rapid Response	Flexible and fast decision making model. May be more appropriate to organisations with fragile external environments.	Less stable structure without developed mechanism of operability

Conclusions

The work conducted under Task 5.2 demonstrates that the sustainability of a future European Network of NCMHs will depend on balanced governance structures, diversified financing strategies, and resilient business continuity mechanisms. Existing European cancer networks offer valuable lessons, particularly regarding the importance of strategic oversight, transparency, member engagement, and adaptability to diverse policy and healthcare environments.

The findings confirm strong alignment between stakeholder expectations identified in the Ecosystem and Needs Analysis and the priorities outlined in Task 5.1, notably the emphasis on supporting the establishment of NCMHs, facilitating knowledge exchange, and strengthening collaboration at both national and European levels. Knowledge sharing, networking, and visibility emerged as the most significant shared benefits for both the network as a whole and individual participants.

The portfolio of governance, financing, and business continuity scenarios presented in this report provides a flexible and modular framework rather than a single prescriptive model. This approach recognises the heterogeneity of Member States and Associated Countries, as well as the evolving nature of the European cancer landscape. Importantly, the scenarios highlight the need for a dynamic interaction between the European Network and national NCMHs, ensuring coordination, mutual support, and alignment with national cancer plans and EU Mission on Cancer objectives.

In conclusion, this report establishes a solid conceptual and operational basis for the future European Network of NCMHs. The proposed scenarios offer practical guidance for designing sustainable structures while allowing for adaptation to national contexts and organisational maturity. The next steps - validation and refinement through Focus Groups and continued stakeholder engagement - will be critical to translating this framework into an effective, resilient, and impactful European Network supporting cancer control and innovation across Europe.

Next steps

The next phase of work will focus on the validation and refinement of the proposed governance, financing, and business continuity scenarios through structured stakeholder engagement. In close cooperation with Work Package 5.3, a series of Focus Group discussions will be organised to critically assess the relevance, feasibility, and adaptability of the scenarios presented in this report.

The Focus Groups will bring together representatives of key stakeholder groups involved in the future European Network of National Cancer Mission Hubs, reflecting the diversity of the Penta Helix model and the heterogeneity of national contexts across Member States and Associated Countries. Their primary objective will be to validate the proposed scenarios against practical needs, organisational realities, and long-term sustainability considerations at both national and European levels.

Specifically, the Focus Groups will:

- assess the applicability of the proposed governance, financing, and business continuity models to the operation of the European Network of NCMHs and its interaction with national hubs.
- identify strengths, weaknesses, and potential risks associated with each scenario.
- explore possible combinations of scenarios and hybrid models suited to different stages of network maturity.
- collect concrete recommendations to improve clarity, operability, and alignment with the objectives of the EU Mission on Cancer.

The outcomes of the Focus Groups will be systematically analysed and used to refine the initial framework presented in this report. Validated and adjusted scenarios will then inform the final recommendations for the establishment and long-term sustainability of the European Network of NCMHs, ensuring that the proposed models are evidence-based, stakeholder-endorsed, and adaptable to diverse national and institutional settings.

Appendix

1. Questionnaire for the Initial Survey (Phase 1)

ECHO S Business-continuity framework for the network - Benchmarking & environmental scan.

This survey is part of the European project ECHO S—Establishing of Cancer Mission Hubs: Networks and Synergies. ECHO S is funded by the Horizon Europe Programme to support the implementation of the EU Mission on Cancer (also referred to as the Mission on Cancer) and of Europe's Beating Cancer Plan (EBCP) in all Member States and Associated Countries.

The survey was developed by Team of Task 5.2 within the scope of the Business-continuity framework - governance, finance and business models, Led by MSC1 - Maria Skłodowska - Curie National Research Institute of Oncology in Poland and participants: Sciensano, HUS-YHTYMA, NCCP-HSE Health Service Executive HSE, LSMU - Lietuvos Sveikatos Mokslu Universitetas, TUSEB - Turkiye Saglik Enstituleri Baskanligi.

The aim of the Survey.

The primary objective of this Task is to define a governance structure that ensures the long-term sustainability of the network, focusing on finance and business strategies. It involves benchmarking against various international health organisations to identify effective funding models, with preference given to organisations that engage civil society.

The following survey will allow us to deepen the information already gathered online about your organisation, enabling us to tailor our model accordingly.

The survey takes about 40 minutes to complete.

For more information about the project, you can reach <https://cancermissionhubs.eu/>

vyriagare

A. BACKGROUND

1. Name of the Network/Organisation *

2. How long has the Network/Organisation exists? *

- less than 3 years
- more than 3 years
- more than 5 years
- I don't know
- others

3. Country of the Headquarter or Secretariat of the Network/Organisation - please specify. *

- Belgium
- Bulgaria
- Czech Republic
- Denmark
- Germany
- Estonia
- Ireland
- Greece
- Spain
- France
- Croatia
- Italy
- Cyprus
- Latvia
- Lithuania
- Luxembourg
- Hungary
- Malta
- Netherlands
- Austria
- Poland
- Portugal
- Romania
- Slovenia
- Slovakia
- Finland
- Sweden
- others

4. What is your role in the Network/Organisation? For Ex. Are you a team of the Board, a member of the Steering Committee, a network member, a task force member, an Executive Board member, etc.? *

B. GOVERNANCE AND STRUCTURE.

5. What are the main elements of the organisational structure of your Network/Organisation ? *

- Network Board
- Steering Board
- General Assembly
- Members representative Board
- Others

6. What roles and responsibilities do the board members have? *

- Strategic management
- Operational oversight
- Financial decisions
- Planning
- Project implementation
- Quality control
- Relationship building
- Representing the organisation
- Resource management
- others

7. What are the fundamental management principles and procedures in your Network/Organisation ? *

- Regular meeting
- Reporting
- Regulatory compliance
- Strategic Planning
- Risk assessment
- Internal audits
- Transparency
- Integrity
- Accountability
- Other

8. Please rank in order of importance all you tick in the question above.

	critical	high	moderate
Regular meetings	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reporting	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Regulatory compliance	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Strategic planning	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Risk assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Internal audits	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Transparency	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Integrity	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Accountability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

9. What mechanisms ensure flexibility in management to meet the diverse needs of the members? *

- Consultations with members
- Quick decision-making
- Personalised support
- Constant communication
- Task delegation
- Adaptation to changes
- Emergency meetings
- Surveys
- Intervention teams
- others

C. FINANCE MODELS

10. What are the main sources of funding for your Network/Organisation? *

- Membership fees
- Grants
- Sponsorship
- EU Funds
- Loans
- Private investments
- Government support
- Crowdfunding
- Service revenues
- MS Contribution
- Others

11. What strategies do you use for fundraising? *

- Organising events
- Seeking sponsors
- Applying for grants
- Collaboration with foundations
- Promotional campaigns
- Diverse services for members (expertise, coaching etc.)
- Business support
- Strategic partnerships
- Active stakeholder engagement
- Online fundraising platforms
- Corporate partnerships or CSR initiatives
- Annual fundraising drives
- others

D. BUSINESS CONTINUITY

12. Are there different types of membership? *

13. What criteria must an organisation meet to become a member of your Network/Organisation ? *

- Agreeing to the regulations of the network
- Meeting specific formal requirements
- Membership fee
- Recommendations from other members
- Active participation
- Cooperation with the Board
- Activity in the field of oncology
- High reputation
- Involvement in project
- data/sample/supply sharing
- others

14. What benefits do you offer your members for different membership types? (please specify) *

15. What strategies do you use to engage members and ensure their active participation? (please specify) *

16. What collaboration models do you have with other networks, institutions, and organisations not members of your Network/Organisation? (please specify) *

E. SERVICES

17. Do you provide services? *

- Only for members
- For everyone

18. What services and support do you offer your members? *

- Thematic workshops
- Training
- Best practices exchange
- Remote consultations
- Networking
- others

19. If you tick other in question 18th, please specify. *

20. What type of training and workshops do you organise for your members? (please specify) *

21. How do you support exchanging knowledge and best practices among members? (please specify) *

22. What tools and resources do you provide members to support their activities? (please specify) *

F. MONITORING

23. 1. What methods do you use to monitor and evaluate the activities of your Network/Organisation? *

- Member surveys
- Regular analysis
- Results analysis
- Evaluations
- External inspections
- Monthly reporting
- Monitoring meetings
- Benchmarking
- Information systems
- others

24. What Key performance indicators (KPIs) do you use to assess the success of your activities? Please tick all that apply. *

- Number of members
- Member satisfaction
- Revenue growth
- Project effectiveness
- Number of partnerships
- Level of engagement
- Financial results
- Number of training sessions
- Level of innovation
- others

G. PR STRATEGY

25. What communication strategies do you use to promote the activities of your Network/Organisation? Please describe. *

26. What communication channels most effectively reach your members and stakeholders? *

- Email
- Online platforms
- Face to face meetings
- Social media
- Discussion forums
- Mobile apps
- Newsletter
- Phone
- Videoconferences
- others

H. FUTURE AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

27. What are your long-term strategy/plans for Network/Organisation development? Open question(please specify) *

28. What strategies do you use to ensure sustainable development and continuity of operations?
Open question (please specify) *

29. What innovations do you plan to implement to improve your activities and services? Open
question (please specify) *

30. What were the biggest challenges in creating your Network/Organisation, and how did you
overcome them? (please specify) *

31. What advice would you give to a newly emerging network to ensure its success? (please
specify) *

32. What are the key success factors that your Network/Organisation has identified as essential
to achieving its goals? (please specify) *

33. What challenges have you encountered in securing sustainable financing? How did you
overcome them? *

2. Questionnaire for In-depth Interviews (Phase 2)

Questions proposed for the in-depth interviews based on the responses received during the First phase of interviews.

Deepening Q10.

- Which of these funding sources is the most significant for your organization? Why?
- How do you structure membership fees for individuals or organizations within your network?
- What strategies do you use to encourage new memberships and retain current members?
- What criteria do you use when selecting sponsors or private investors?
- How do you ensure alignment between your organization's mission and the interests of sponsors or investors?
- What types of services generate revenue for your organization?
- How do you ensure these services align with your organization's core objectives and values?
- Can you specify what funding sources fall under the 'Others' category?
- Are there any funding constraints that limit your operational capacity?
- How does your organization ensure transparency in the management of funds from different sources?
- What trends in funding do you anticipate will impact your organization in the next 5–10 years?
- How do partnerships influence your funding strategy?

Deepening Q13

- How do you monitor if the member fulfil obligation during the membership (relevant with multilevel membership)?
- How do you address instances where members do not fulfil the obligations outlined in this document?
- How do you ensure alignment between annual strategic goals and member interest?
- How do you track and evaluate member participation in your initiatives?

Deepening Q15

- What benchmarks or KPIs do you use to measure engagement success?

- How do you keep members engaged in a long term , beyond one-off events or activities
- What initiatives have proven most effective fostering sustained participation.

Deepening Q16

- Responses missing

Deepening Q17

- Responses missing

Deepening Q18

- How are the fees structured depending on the membership type?

Deepening Q19

- When ticked, “Other”, please elaborate.

Deepening Q20

- Are in-house experts engaged or is outsourcing enabled?

Deepening Q21

- Do knowledge exchange workshops happen regularly?

Deepening Q22-23

- How do you implement changes based on received feedback?

3. Questionnaire for Ecosystem and Needs Analysis (Phase 3)

1. Which group of stakeholders do you represent :
 - a. Healthcare (HCPs, Hospitals, Pharmacies, eHealth)
 - b. Industry
 - c. Patients (PAGs, Carers)
 - d. Researchers (Universities, Research, Institutes, Scientific Societies)
 - e. Policymakers (Ministry of Health, Ministry of Science, etc.)
 - f. Others (Regulatory agencies, Governmental bodies, Regional and local administration, public services)
2. What activities can you – as a representative of the selected Stakeholder group – add to the EU Network of NCMHs? (open ended)
3. Name all potential challenges that the European Network of NCMHs can encounter? (open ended)
4. Name all potential challenges that you can encounter? (open ended)
5. What are the benefits for the European Network of national hubs (NCMHs)? (open ended)
6. What are the benefits for you of joining the European Network of national hubs (NCMHs)? (open ended)

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